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PERCEIVE

Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections through AI and Virtual Experiences

D2.3 Training Program

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Executive Summary

The PERCEIVE training program focuses on enhancing educational activities related to the preservation and communication of coloured cultural heritage collections. The program has included online webinars, organised as Expert Presentations. During the webinars, named “Perceive Talks”, members of the consortium offered collaboration and shared insights on specific topics related to various scenarios, in particular dealing with significance of colour in works of art, innovative diagnostic techniques, and the role of digital technologies in enhancing visitor experiences. At the end of every episode, which are 13 in totals, from June 2025 to January 2026, interactive Q&A sessions were performed and many participants engaged with speakers through real-time questions, fostering a dynamic exchange of ideas and clarifications on complex subjects. The webinar provided access to supplementary discussions on specific case studies via social medias. Indeed, the networking opportunities to share contents and episodes has turned itself in a great opportunity to talk to specialists and connect with the PERCEIVE project in general. It has been a further occasion to share experiences and explore potential collaborations. Post-webinar surveys gather participant feedback, helping to improve sessions and ensuring that the contents meet the interest and the needs of the remote participants. Overall, the PERCEIVE webinar effectively combines expert knowledge with interactive elements to enhance learning and professional development.

Document History

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Training Program

Why a webinar?

Cristiana Barandoni, Sofia Pescarin, Ivana Cerato (CNR-ISPC)

WP2 is responsible for setting up the PERCEIVE Know-How training program, for Museum professionals and SMEs; due to this WP2 has the role of planning and organising activities to ensure that all the activities related to the training program are aligned and able to respond to the needs of the various working groups. This involves: the identification of objectives, audiences, and scopes; organise programs and teaching units; prepare plans for teaching learning contents; define criteria; programming the temporal organization of educational activities and establish methods for evaluating the quality of the activities. This is why we propose teaching programs joining international collaborations with PERCEIVE partners.

All PERCEIVE results need to be accessible to all stakeholders, under the respective IPR regulations, through them. A specific training program oriented to Cultural Institutions and SMEs will further support the know-how transfer from science to industry. The dissemination and exploitation plan will be defined in accordance with this. Datasets and technologies will be fully documented, enabling collaboration, knowledge exchange and transfer. Since PERCEIVE platform will provide a variety of reusable, high-level Tools and Services for direct artwork and environment manipulation and experimentation, along with the relative API for the specialised stakeholders, it is necessary to schedule training activities aimed at reaching different stakeholders expectations.

Living co-creation sessions with design tools and a specific training program oriented to Cultural Institutions and SMEs will further support the know-how transfer from science to industry. The dissemination and exploitation plan will be defined in accordance with this. One of the results of PERCEIVE is the creation of Repository, Platform, Tools and Services whose aim is to enhance the effectiveness of the curatorial processes, carried out by museums and other cultural parties. Here are the different stages:

- widening the perception on colour impact and manipulation
- reducing the time and cost required for each of the assumed activities and
- enabling non-expert users to use high-level curation and simulation applications.

The training program will strengthen their digital capabilities and the acquisition protocols/exhibition guidelines as a reference point for the institutions and for the indications they provide to external companies involved in exhibition and lighting design.

To do so, we decided to use the form of a webinar thanks to the advantages of having activities online: webinars have emerged as a significant modality within the realm of education, particularly in the context of remote learning. This format presents several advantages that enhance the educational experience:

Accessibility (which is one of the terms of PERCEIVE) thanks to their asynchronous nature that allows participants to engage in our content from diverse geographical locations. This accessibility mitigates barriers related to distance and enables individuals from varied backgrounds to partake in learning opportunities that may otherwise be unavailable. Another aspect is the flexibility of the chance to watch them during the live session or later: all our webinars are recorded and uploaded in the PERCEIVE YouTube website, allowing public to access materials at their convenience. This flexibility accommodates diverse schedules and learning paces, fostering a more personalized

educational experience. From economic point of view and from the availability of speakers engaged, we have reduced costs associated with traditional meetings, such as travel expenses, accommodation, and physical materials. This economic advantage allowed all Perceivers to join and offer their time. Another benefit is their ability to feature subject matter experts and practitioners from diverse fields: our program has provided learners with insights and knowledge that reflect all the topic sustained by PERCEIVE giving them the opportunity to explain them to the public. To be reactive and prompt we incorporate interactive elements such as live Q&A sessions at the end of every episode which promoted active engagement and facilitate meaningful interactions between experts and participants, ultimately enhancing the overall learning process.

In addition to these interactive components, the digital nature of webinars allowed us to reach a larger audience without the constraints of physical space. This scalability enables the dissemination of knowledge to a wider demographic, thereby increasing the impact of educational initiatives.

Introduction

Cristiana Barandoni, (CNR-ISPC), Sofia Pescarin (CNR-ISPC)

The WP2 oversees the developing the theoretical framework that supports the entire project in reaching its objectives of colour reconstruction, rendering, remapping, preserving, exhibiting and re-appropriating through PERCEIVE experiences. It defines and involves the stakeholders for each scenario (creating focus groups), studies their current workflows and identifies their needs, in terms of desired outcomes and working modalities. It involves them in co-creation and co-interpretation activities. The theory and needs are used to refine the scenarios, verifying if they are representative enough or if a different scenario needs to be addressed and finally preparing the requirements for the different components of the project (PERCEIVE core, tools, services, digital experiences, training). The WP is also responsible for setting up the PERCEIVE Know-How training program, for Museum professionals and SMEs. Referring to T2.4 PERCEIVE training program will create and develop a PERCEIVE training program for Museum professionals and SMEs. Participating in a scientific and plural voiced webinar offers professionals several compelling motivations that contribute to their ongoing development and effectiveness in their respective fields. Firstly, these webinars provide access to cutting-edge research and advancements, enabling professionals to stay informed about the latest methodologies, technologies, and findings relevant to their area of expertise. This continual exposure to new information fosters an environment of lifelong learning, which is essential in an ever-evolving scientific landscape, thanks also to the PERCEIVE YouTube channel (https://www.youtube.com/@Perceive_horizon). Secondly, the interactive nature of webinars facilitates meaningful engagement with experts and peers, allowing participants to ask questions, share insights, and discuss challenges they may face in their work. This collaborative atmosphere not only enhances understanding but also promotes networking opportunities that can lead to future collaborations and partnerships. Lastly, attending scientific webinars allows professionals to apply the knowledge gained directly to their practice, equipping them with innovative strategies and solutions that can improve their performance and contribute to the advancement of their field. The PERCEIVE webinars are dedicated to the critical examination of works of art that suffer from significant colour changes. As artworks age, they often undergo notable changes in colour, which can profoundly affect their aesthetic value and historical context. Understanding these changes is essential for art historians, conservators, and scientists alike. Fundamental part of the Perceive project is the Training Program, aims to explore the various factors contributing to colour decay, including environmental influences, material degradation, and the intrinsic properties of the pigments used. By analysing specific case studies, we will highlight the impact of colour change on the interpretation

and appreciation of artworks. The training programme is a crucial component of the Perceive activities, as it supports the preventive diagnostics necessary to assess the condition of coloured artworks, activities that are essential for the timely identification of any signs of deterioration, enabling targeted and punctual interventions to preserve the integrity of artworks. Today it is of a certain importance for museum conservators, as well as professionals in the field, remain well-informed about the conditions affecting polychrome works. The series of webinars is specifically designed to address all topics related to Perceive, covering the various diagnostic activities undertaken and transforming this knowledge into accessible sessions.

The webinars can be attended both live and on demand via the YouTube channel of the project, facilitating participation from a broader audience. This flexibility not only enhances the accessibility of information but also encourages greater interaction and discussion among professionals, contributing to a culture of prevention and informed conservation. Reference point of the webinars is the possibility to discuss the latest scientific methodologies employed to investigate colour fading or general changes, such as spectroscopic analysis and imaging techniques. These tools provide critical insights into the extent of deterioration and assist in developing effective conservation strategies. One of the key points of the training program is the chance of interdisciplinary collaboration in the field of art conservation, combining insights from art history, archaeology, physics, chemistry, and digital technology to enhance our understanding of colour study and its implications for the preservation of these very fragile works of art, some of which are considered world masterpieces. All the episodes are scheduled from April 2025 to January 2026 and will deepen the opportunity to explore advanced research and innovative methodologies: one of the objective of PERCEIVE is to enhance the digital capabilities of scientists and cultural institutions through a service-oriented AI architecture and toolkit, while also developing a new design theory for both on-site and remote VR/AR/MR experiences. This is grounded in the principles of “Care,” “Accessibility,” and “Authenticity,” aimed at benefiting the creative industries and expanding access to Cultural Heritage and Art beyond traditional museum settings, thereby fostering broader social integration.

Collections featuring polychrome works are of particular concern due to their inherent fragility, necessitating the establishment of shared methodologies for their preservation and exhibition. For example, textiles may deteriorate within a mere decade, and only minimal remnants of the original polychromy on classical statues are retraceable. The complexity involved in their study, particularly in reconstructing their original appearance, alongside the imperative of effectively communicating these aspects to future generations, remains a critical focus. Each episode of the webinar will concentrate on a specific theme, examining various dimensions of ancient polychromy through multidisciplinary lenses. Notably, the integration of advanced technologies will be emphasized to enhance the understanding and management of museum collections such those we choose for PERCEIVE: classical statues, textiles, autochrome, photography, paintings and digital art. Each episode of the webinar series is specifically dedicated to a distinct topic, collectively encapsulating the comprehensive experience of the project. The discussions encompass a wide range of subjects, including tools (**PERCEIVE Co-Design Tool**), insights into the development and application of prototypes (i.e. **Caring and Authenticity**) and detailed explanation of **Colour Knowledge Repository** which is of pivotal relevance in this field. Furthermore, through the case study of the Iseum of Pompei, the series aims to provide an opportunity for a modular exhibit solution to the enhancement of museum practices. This case study illustrates practical applications of the discussed topics, demonstrating how integrated approaches can effectively contribute to the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage within museum contexts. All episodes are organized with two speakers who will address the same topic from two different perspectives, followed by a Q&A session. The

modality is specifically designed to address all topics related to Perceive and transforming this knowledge into accessible sessions. Participants are encouraged to submit their questions in the chat throughout the presentations, fostering a more dynamic exchange of ideas. The speakers will be prepared to respond to these inquiries at the conclusion of their presentations, thereby enhancing the overall educational experience.

Episodes:

PERCEIVE Theory and Data Acquisition and use of colour...

1 [*PERCEIVE theory and data acquisition and use for colour change simulation and collection management*](#)

PERCEIVE Developing a Game-Based Experience for Caring About...

2 [*Developing A Game-Based Experience for Caring about Colour Fading in Munch's The Scream*](#)

PERCEIVE MuLaX Revolutionizing the Study of Lost Polychromy in...

3 [*MuLaX Revolutionising the Study of Lost Polychromy*](#)

PERCEIVE Autochromes Observed

4. [*Revolution and Realities; Digitisation, Separation and Restoration: Autochromes Observed*](#)

PERCEIVE Tools, Services and Mediation on the Scream Simulati...

5. [*PERCEIVE tools, services and mediation on the SCREAM simulation of colour change*](#)

PERCEIVE Non Invasive Analytical Approaches to Photofading Dyes in...

6. [*Non-Invasive Analytical Approaches to Photofading Dyes in Museum Dress Textile*](#)

PERCEIVE Tracing the Changing Colours of The Scream (ca. 1910)

[7. *Tracing the Changing Colours of The Scream \(ca. 1910\)*](#)

PERCEIVE SimTex: Virtual 3D Restoration and Simulation of...

[8. *SimTex: Virtual 3D Restoration and Simulation of Fading in Fugitive Textiles*](#)

PERCEIVE An Integrated Approach to Reconstructing Ancient...

[9. *An Integrated Approach to Reconstructing Ancient Polychromy on Marble Sculpture*](#)

Introduction to the Colour Knowledge Repository of PERCEIVE

[10. *Introduction to the Colour Knowledge Repository*](#)

[11. *Prototyping Caring Hybrid Experiences for Coloured Museum Collections*](#)

[12. *Prototyping Authentic Hybrid Experiences for Coloured Museum Collections*](#)

[13. *Tools and Services for the Design of Digital Heritage Experiences. PERCEIVE Desing ToolBox*](#)

1. Episodes

Cristiana Barandoni (CNR-ISPC)

1.1 PERCEIVE theory and data acquisition and use for colour change simulation and collection management

Link: https://youtu.be/g_ZEyaW-D_E

Date 16th April

Abstract & Speakers: Irina Sandu (MUNCH), Letizia Monico (CNR)

The webinar explores the data acquisition performed in several campaigns around the main case study of Scenario 2 (the Scream, in 2 of its versions) and the research on Cd yellow fading making use of mock-ups. It will show the applications emerged from the research of PERCEIVE project regarding the simulation of colour change processes and collection management focused on light-induced changes and preservation of coloured collection.

Letizia Monico is a senior researcher at the Institute of Chemical Sciences and Technologies “Giulio Natta” (SCITEC) of the National Research Council (CNR) and a visiting scientist in the AXIS research group of the Physics Department at the University of Antwerp.

Since earning a joint PhD in Chemistry from the Universities of Perugia and Antwerp in 2012, she has established herself as a specialist in the study of alteration processes and the characterization of artists' materials, particularly inorganic pigments in paintings, using vibrational and synchrotron radiation-based X-ray micro-spectroscopies. She is a member of MOLAB, an infrastructure for in-situ non-invasive measurements of cultural heritage objects within the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science, and a co-coordinator of the Historical Materials BAG at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility in Grenoble.

She is (co-)author of over 45 peer-reviewed papers and book chapters. From 2013 to 2022, her research on the alteration processes of pigments received numerous awards, including the Eric Samuel Award from the Microscopy Society of America, the SILS-SPECS PhD Award from the Italian Synchrotron Radiation Society, the Primo Levi Prize, and the Rossi Manaresi Medal, both from the Italian Chemical Society.

Irina Crina Anca Sandu is a Conservation Scientist (PhD in Chemistry, 2003) working at Munch museum since 2016. She led several projects focused on the scientific study of Edvard Munch Collection, with internal and external funding. Main research interests she developed in the past 8 years are: interdisciplinary and multiscale studies and characterization of original artist materials and art-objects collections; study of colour change phenomena in modern paints; 3D modeling/rendering and monitoring of polychrome/painted artifacts using complementary analytical approaches; development of non-invasive methodologies for the evaluation of conservation-restoration treatments (cleaning); creation and development of digital databases and immersive experiences; development and implementation of innovative Outreach and training/educational strategies for the investigation and conservation of cultural heritage. She is Project lead for PERCEIVE on behalf of MUNCH museum and coordinates the work around Scenario 2 dealing with paintings and works on paper subject to colour change (Scenario2-Paintings - PERCEIVE).

Topic: Colour change (or Discoloration) in paintings and works on paper

Content of the webinar

The inaugural episode will be exclusively dedicated to the data acquisition conducted during various research campaigns, with particular emphasis on Scenario 2 of the project (paintings). The presentation will give an overview of the PERCEIVE project focusing on the Scenario 2, dealing with paintings and works on paper subject to colour change. The case studies from MUNCH (2 versions of the Scream, one on cardboard and a hand-coloured print) and the Art Institute of Chicago (watercolour on paper by Cezanne) will be presented as examples for the simulation of colour changes using different approaches and tools. Thus, the contribution of the project in this scenario towards advancing novel tools and technologies for conservation and documentation will be shown on specific case studies with colour change phenomena. In particular, the prototype Scream Time Machine will be used as example of the interdisciplinary methodology used by the PERCEIVE researchers starting from acquisition of analytical data by non-destructive and non-invasive techniques up to creating 3D replicas and a board game for multisensorial applications. One of the most visible forms of degradation in artworks is discoloration, a phenomenon that alters the original colours. It is often triggered by exposure to environmental factors (e.g., light, temperature, humidity) and frequently modify the chemical and/or mechanical properties of the paint. On one hand, for the sake of preservation and defining the optimal exhibition policy of a work of art, it is crucial to study the aging behaviour of its materials and predict their future change. On the other hand, for tracing back the visual narrative and the history of an artwork, it is important to attempt its restoration and visualize its original colours. This webinar outlines the foundational experimental approaches employed to develop digital models that accurately simulate discoloration of selected pigments (e.g. vermilion, ultramarine, cadmium yellows) in *The Scream* (ca. 1910) painting by Edvard Munch (details about the digital modelling are available in the webinars from September 16th and October 3rd). The presentation will emphasize the integration of data from multiple analytical methods and materials, including elemental and structural mapping (via X-ray methods), vibrational spectroscopy, colorimetry, visible hyperspectral imaging, results from artificially aged paint mock-ups and insights from archival records on colour films.

[1.2. Developing a Game-Based Experience for Caring about Colour Fading in Munch's The Scream](#)

Link <https://youtu.be/fqFW-gm5mGs?si=tK210N4Y3GzmfMLL>

Date 6th May

Abstract & Speakers: Dr. Birgitte Aga (Head of Innovation & Research, MUNCH and Michael David Elliott (Game developer, MUNCH)

How can games function as a medium for care within museum contexts? This webinar examines the use of game-based mediation as a strategy for engaging young audiences with conservation and material vulnerability in artworks. Using the *PERCEIVE Prototype for Caring* developed at MUNCH as a point of departure, the session reflects on how playful systems, narrative framing, and cooperative interaction can support children's engagement with complex heritage science. The speakers will address the opportunities and challenges of designing game-based museum experiences, the role of interdisciplinarity in their development, and how narrative mediation can contribute to more affective and meaningful encounters with fragile cultural heritage.

Birgitte Aga is an activist, creative technologist, and researcher with a Ph.D. in the artistic and ethical application of AI. As Head of Innovation & Research at MUNCH in Oslo, she continuously explores

new ways for the museum to engage its audience, create value, and preserve its collection for future generations.

Meeka Elliott, is co-founder of Tooth Games, and a game developer and visual designer working for MUNCH on the Perceive research project. The project aims to create a video game and installation that evoke wonder, loss, and care for colour change in Edvard Munch's "The Scream".

Topic: Developing A Game-Based Experience for Caring about Colour Fading in Munch's The Scream.

Content of the webinar This webinar explores *PERCEIVE Prototype for Caring* — an interactive, game-based mediation experience rooted in the colour fading of Edvard Munch's *The Scream* ('1910?' version). Designed for young audiences aged 6–10, the prototype fosters both understanding and empathy: children learn why colours change over time, and what it means to care for fragile works of art. Developed by the MUNCH Museum in Oslo as part of the European research project PERCEIVE, *Tiny Conservators* transforms conservation science into an immersive, participatory experience. Installed in The Amfi, MUNCH's circular glass lobby, the prototype uses projection, light, and sound to create a world inside the microscopic layers of *The Scream*. Here, children become "Tiny Conservators" who must protect the painting's pigments from the destructive forces of Time, Humidity, and Light — reimagined as the flamboyant *Monarchs of Decay*. The project's goal extends beyond communicating scientific knowledge: it aims to cultivate a *culture of care* among children and families. Through cooperative play and narrative mediation, participants experience care not only for the artwork but for one another — reinforcing empathy, collaboration, and shared responsibility as core conservation values. The prototype was developed through a collaborative process between game designers, art mediators, technical and exhibition designers, and conservation scientists. It draws on participatory design methods, with Norwegian schoolchildren actively contributing to character creation, story concepts, and gameplay mechanics. During the webinar, we will discuss how museums use technology and storytelling to engage young audiences, the interdisciplinary design process behind *Tiny Conservators*, and the broader aims of PERCEIVE. The conversation will reflect on how playful, sensory environments can make heritage science accessible, affective, and meaningful to a new generation of museum visitors.

[1.3 MuLaX](#)

Link https://youtu.be/-Ui7yu8I-JU?si=W1ATG9qTC9ks_yIS

Date 20th May

Abstract & Speakers: Bruno Fanini (ISPC-CNR), Daniele Ferdani (CNR)

MuLaX is a Web3D application to map and discover diagnostic processes behind lost polychromy and colour changes studies on coloured collections in museums. The MuLaX is a tool that enables to visualize, inspect, manipulate and compare analytical/colour layers directly on the 3D model of the artwork. Built on top of the open-source ATON framework, MuLaX supports interactive discovery of analytical analyses, through an annotation system for spot analyses (e.g., microscopy, XRF and FORS), and multi-layer visualization for imaging techniques like VIL and UVL (either through lens or split mode). Being web-based the application is accessible on every device, from smartphones, ensuring accessibility and interoperability with modern web standards. MuLaX also integrates dynamic image-based masks, enabling efficient annotation and semantic painting. Through its connection with the PERCEIVE cloud, it facilitates remote data management and processing,

enhancing collaboration among researchers. Additionally, WebXR support provides immersive experiences in AR, MR, and VR.

Bruno Fanini, holds a PhD in Computer Science and is a researcher in the Institute of Heritage Science at the National Research Council (ISPC-CNR). He is part of the Digital Heritage Innovation Lab (DHILab) and his research and development activities focus on real-time 3D graphics, immersive visualization, natural interaction and the design of 3D user interfaces. He has designed and developed open-source Web3D/WebXR tools (such as the ATON framework), serious games, virtual museums and interactive applications targeting Cultural Heritage. He currently oversees a number of projects dealing with interactive 3D visualization, online 3D presentation, interaction models and immersive XR.

Daniele Ferdani, Senior Researcher at the Institute of Heritage Science of the National Research Council (ISPC-CNR). He holds a PhD in Archaeology and is an expert in digital archaeology. His research focuses on the development of integrated methodologies for the 3D acquisition, analysis, and reconstruction of classical and medieval contexts, as well as their dissemination through virtual museums and virtual reality systems.

Topic: MulaX Tool

Content of the webinar

The episode, moderated by C. Barandoni, focused on MuLaX (Multi-Layer eXtensible eXplorer): a Web3D/WebXR tool designed and developed in the PERCEIVE project for interactive and immersive discovery of diagnostic processes on multi-layered 3D collections. In the first part of the episode, D. Ferdani presented the workflow adopted for the creation of a multiband three-dimensional model of a statue, focusing on the methodological steps required to integrate photogrammetry and multiband imaging into a single coherent 3D representation. The presentation was intended as a practical explanation of how the multiband 3D model is produced. The aim was to provide participants with a clear understanding of the overall process, from image acquisition to the generation of an interactive 3D asset, which can then be exploited in Web3dD applications. The workflow starts with the photogrammetric acquisition of the statue in different spectral bands, namely visible light (VIS), ultraviolet-induced visible luminescence (UVL), and visible-induced luminescence (VIL). Each dataset is acquired separately, following standard photogrammetric principles, but with specific lighting and acquisition setups adapted to the different spectral responses. Once acquired, the datasets are processed independently. The visible-light dataset is used to generate the reference 3D geometry, as it provides the highest geometric accuracy and surface completeness. The UVL and VIL datasets, which are primarily intended to reveal material and pigment-related information, are processed separately and later aligned to the visible model. A central step of the workflow is the integration of the different photogrammetric datasets into a common 3D reference system. This is achieved by identifying homologous reference points across the datasets, allowing all spectral information to be spatially registered onto the same geometry. This step ensures that the relationship between geometry and spectral data is preserved, even when datasets are acquired at different times or using different equipment. Following alignment, the workflow proceeds with multiband texture projection. The VIS, UVL, and VIL images are mapped onto the reference mesh using a shared UV layout. This results in multiple perfectly aligned textures applied to the same 3D model, enabling direct comparison between spectral layers without geometric discrepancies. The speaker emphasized that this approach allows users to switch between spectral representations while maintaining full spatial coherence.

In the final phase, the model is optimized for interactive visualization, including mesh simplification and texture management, in order to make it suitable for web-based and real-time applications. At this stage, the 3D model becomes not only a documentation output, but also a structured container for multiband information, ready to support analysis, interpretation, and dissemination activities

The presentation concluded by stressing that this multiband 3D reconstruction workflow represents the technical foundation for subsequent stages of the training programme. In particular, it directly precedes and enables the contribution by Bruno Fanini, who focuses on how the resulting multiband 3D models are employed as core content within the MuLaX application for interactive data exploration and analysis.

In the second part, B. Fanini presented in detail the MuLaX tool, starting from the the goals related to the discovery of lost or invisible information, the need for improved readability of the artwork and the exploration of new ways to access and examine multi-dimensional data. After a brief background and previous experiences on interactive discovery approaches and metaphors, the open-source ATON framework is introduced and the components involved into the design and development of MuLaX. The tool is then described with its components and features, with a focus on multi-disciplinary approach adopted to craft some of the functionalities developed. Multi-layer discovery, semantic masks, full support for AR/VR inspection via WebXR and cloud integration are presented. Closing remarks are dedicated to the extensibility of tool, and how this modular design allowed the tool to embrace other scenarios (like Scenario 2 – “paintings and works on paper”) and enable inspection of 2D multi-layered collections directly on the web.

1.4 The Autochrome: Revolution and Realities- Catlin Langford & Digitisation, Separation and Restoration: Autochromes Observed-Giorgio Trumpy

Link <https://youtu.be/hV5EQQ1Is3I?si=fD9W3gQQOnxbbr0P>

Date 17th June

Abstract & Speakers: Catlin Langford (Victoria and Albert Museum) and Giorgio Trumpy (NTNU)

Abstract. The Autochrome Lumière was the first commercially successful colour photography process and was hailed as a revolution in photography and art when it was released commercially in 1907. Autochromes, however, are extremely light sensitive and the colours are prone to fading. This was an issue during their main period of use (1907-1930) but also poses problems today. Given their fragility, many international public institutions do not display their autochrome collections and instead exhibit facsimile copies. There are also restrictions around public access and digitisation processes. These practices underscore the need for non-invasive methods to provide public access and insight without compromising preservation. At the Colourlab at NTNU, spectral imaging is being used to separate the overlapping visual elements of autochrome plates—the optical properties of colour dyes and the photographic image itself. This information will be used for a range of results, which will include the virtual restoration of damaged autochromes and a consideration of the potential of digital heritage. To conclude, we will discuss our survey of current digitisation practices relating to autochromes. This information will inform ways to address the unique obstacles that autochrome plates presents in terms of their digitisation.

Catlin Langford is a curator, writer and researcher specialising in photography. She has held curatorial and teaching positions at the Centre for Contemporary Photography, Victoria and Albert Museum, Royal Collection Trust, and Royal College of Art. Her debut publication ‘Colour Mania:

Photographing the World in Autochrome' (Thames & Hudson/V&A) was published in 2022. She is presently working with the V&A's autochrome collection as part of PERCEIVE.

Dr **Giorgio Trumpy** is Associate Professor at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology and founding member of Scan2Screen GmbH. Imaging Scientist with solid experience in bridging the gap between art and science. Fields of expertise span from optics to spectroscopy, from colorimetry to image processing, from heritage conservation to visual arts.

Lucia Burgio is Lead Conservation Scientist at the Victoria and Albert Museum, London, where she heads the Science Laboratory and directs the scientific analysis and research of the V&A collections. She has published extensively on her special interests, which include historical pigments and American and Asian lacquer. She is a Fellow of the Royal Society of Chemistry and is the UK representative to the EuChemS Working Party on Chemistry for Cultural Heritage. She chairs the Royal Society of Chemistry's Heritage Science Expert Working Group, using this position to promote the role and importance of analytical science in the cultural heritage sector and disseminate heritage science to various audiences.

Topic: Autochromes

Content of the webinar

The fourth webinar, moderated by Lucia Burgio, Lead Scientist at the Victoria and Albert Museum, and co-chair of Scenario 4, served as an essential introduction to autochromes—rare and delicate photographic objects that remain relatively unknown due to their fragile materiality. Catlin Langford presented **The Autochrome: Revolution and Realities**, offering historical and curatorial insights, while Giorgio Trumpy delivered **Digitisation, Separation and Restoration: Autochromes Observed**, focusing on technical approaches to digital restoration. Their presentations addressed the complexities and possibilities of digitising Autochrome Lumière plates, the first commercially successful colour photography process, introduced in 1907. Because of their sensitivity to light and tendency to fade, autochromes are seldom exhibited, with institutions often relying on facsimiles and restricting access. At NTNU's Colourlab, spectral imaging is being employed to non-invasively separate the visual layers of autochromes, enabling virtual restoration and supporting digital heritage initiatives. The webinar also outlined additional activities within Scenario 4, including a survey of current digitisation practices aimed at improving access and long-term preservation. With 1200 impressions, the event demonstrated strong engagement with a niche yet significant area of photographic heritage.

[1.5 PERCEIVE tools, services and mediation on the SCREAM simulation of colour change](#)

Link <https://youtu.be/W8To5ulG0C4?si=oEI8mHzlBhRCSEWO>

Date 16th September

Abstract & Speakers: Petros Stavroulakis (FORTH), Nynne Olhson (MUNCH)

This webinar will present the tools and services created during PERCEIVE for showcasing the simulations of colour change on the Scream case study and also the mediation project developed for the final immersive experience designed as a game for kids with age between 6 and 10.

Petros Stavroulakis has a lengthy academic and commercial track record in computer- vision and optical 3D metrology systems engineering, as well as visual AI training and integration. His multi-faceted experience includes managing complete optical measurement system R&D projects from start to finish. His technical expertise and research focus lies in visual AI data acquisition, visual AI model training and visual AI solutions deployment and servicing (ML Ops), as well as in classical computer vision, optical design, optical alignment, 2D/3D measurement algorithms. He has since successfully provided services to and partnered with various international companies, research institutions and governmental agencies in the UK, Italy, Germany and Greece. In the Perceive project, he works as an external services provider for FORTH IESL, working on 3D printing, hyperspectral image processing, Python coding and AI solution development.

Nynne Ryhl Olsson holds a Master's degree in Art History from the University of Copenhagen. She works in the field of art mediation at MUNCH as Concepts Developer Learning. In this role, Nynne collaborates with exhibitions and projects such as PERCEIVE, focusing on meaningful and engaging interactions with visual art by creating engaging experiences through narrative, text, space and program.

Topic: paintings and works on paper

Content of the webinar

This episode deals with the tools and services created during PERCEIVE for showcasing the simulations of colour change on the Scream case study and also the mediation project developed for the final immersive experience Tiny Conservators, designed as a game for kids with age between 6 and 10.

1.6 Non-Invasive Analytical Approaches to Photofading Dyes in Museum Dress Textiles

Link <https://youtu.be/a3Ynfl7ytRs?si=IUEA5XNASy6VH-ES>

Date 22nd September

Abstract & Speakers: Brenda Doherty (CNR-SCITEC), Catarina Pinto (CNR-SCITEC)

The PERCEIVE textile scenario addresses the challenges of preserving museum textiles dyed with natural and synthetic colourants, which fade and degrade over time, altering their original appearance. By reconstructing their aesthetics and simulating further degradation through scientific investigations, the research enhances public appreciation and informs museum conservation strategies. This webinar will present the case studies, including a faded silk kimono and a printed cotton dress and on the acquisition of non-invasive spectroscopic, colourimetric, and imaging data from both historical collections and artificially aged textile mock-ups.

Brenda Doherty is a researcher at the Italian National Research Council's Institute of Chemical Sciences and Technologies (CNR-SCITEC). Her work focuses on developing and applying non-invasive and micro-invasive spectroscopic methods for diagnosing and conserving heritage materials. She specializes in spectroscopic studies of dye and pigment degradation in paintings and textiles by vibrational spectroscopic techniques. With extensive experience in collaborating on numerous national and European heritage science projects, she plays a key role in coordinating access to in-situ diagnostics through the MOLAB mobile laboratories within the transnational access activities of E-RIHS ERIC.

Catarina Pinto is a researcher at the Italian National Research Council's Institute of Chemical Sciences and Technologies (CNR-SCITEC). She holds a Master's degree in Forensic Chemistry and is completing her PhD in photophysics and photochemistry, focusing on molecules of colour. Her research specializes in the photodegradation studies of organic dyes and pigments, in textiles and paintings, by spectroscopic techniques for the safeguarding of cultural heritage.

Lucia Burgio is Lead Conservation Scientist at the Victoria and Albert Museum, London, where she heads the Science Laboratory and directs the scientific analysis and research of the V&A collections. She has published extensively on her special interests, which include historical pigments and American and Asian lacquer. She is a Fellow of the Royal Society of Chemistry and is the UK representative to the EuChemS Working Party on Chemistry for Cultural Heritage. She chairs the Royal Society of Chemistry's Heritage Science Expert Working Group, using this position to promote the role and importance of analytical science in the cultural heritage sector and disseminate heritage science to various audiences.

Content of the webinar

The sixth webinar, moderated by Lucia Burgio, Lead Scientist at the Victoria and Albert Museum, and chair of Scenario 3, focused on the challenges of preserving museum textiles dyed with natural and synthetic colourants, which fade and degrade over time, altering their original appearance. Brenda Doherty and Catarina Pinto presented **Non-Invasive Analytical Approaches to Photofading Dyes in Museum Dress Textiles** and described how, by reconstructing the textiles' aesthetics and simulating further degradation through scientific investigations, the PERCEIVE teams were able to conduct research which enhances public appreciation for these sensitive objects and informs museum conservation strategies. The webinar presented two case studies, a faded silk kimono and a printed cotton dress and focused on the acquisition of non-invasive spectroscopic, colourimetric and imaging data from both historical collections and artificially aged textile mock-ups. The research presented by Doherty and Pinto showed how the different PERCEIVE partners worked together to investigate colour changes on textiles and help with the reconstruction of the original appearance of the objects, for the benefit of a wide variety of audiences.

[1.7 Tracing the Changing Colours of The Scream \(ca. 1910\): Computational Reconstructions from Historical Photographic Records](#)

Link <https://youtu.be/r-KqqvENr1M?si=DDmhIVRjJd5hfXyI>

Date: 3rd October

Speakers & Abstract: Irina Ciortan (NTNU), Panagiotis Siozos (FORTH)

This webinar presents two complementary computational approaches for studying the temporal evolution of Edvard Munch's *The Scream* (ca. 1910) and its changing appearance under the effects of light, moisture, and material ageing. The first approach combines historical black and white photography with recent multispectral imaging to detect colour changes in the painting over time. By simulating the spectral response of the 1938 orthochromatic photograph from modern spectral data, and calibrating it with historic film sensitivity curves, we reveal significant lightness differences that point to fading of yellows and unexpected brightening of blues—phenomena that refine our understanding of the material ageing of the work. The second approach focuses on colour reconstruction using four historical colour photographs from 1971, 1989, 1993, and 2003. To address the challenges of film degradation, the method employs stable reference areas of the painting for advanced colour correction, enabling more faithful digital renderings of its appearance at several

points in the 20th century. Together, these methods provide a pluralistic and data-driven framework for digitally reconstructing the past appearances of *The Scream*, demonstrating how integrating historical photographs with advanced spectral and computational imaging can open new perspectives for cultural heritage research.

Irina-Mihaela Ciortan is a Postdoctoral Researcher at the Colourlab, NTNU, where she previously completed a PhD degree in Computer Science (2023), with a thesis entitled "Spectral and Multi-light Imaging for Cultural Heritage: Material Analysis and Appearance Reconstruction". Irina holds a joint MSc diploma in Spectral Science and Multimedia Technologies awarded by the 4-university Erasmus Mundus Consortium "Colour in Informatics and Media Technology" (2013) and a BSc in Computer Science issued by the Faculty of Cybernetics, Statistics and Informatics in Bucharest, Romania (2011). Currently, Irina works in the HORIZON EU project PERCEIVE (Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Coloured Collections through AI and Virtual Experiences), she is mainly capturing and analysing visual data towards designing computational methods for the digital simulation of colour changes in various artworks: paintings, textiles, historical photographs.

Panagiotis Siozos is a Postdoctoral Researcher at IESL-FORTH specializing in laser-based spectroscopy and digital tools for cultural heritage. Within the HORIZON Europe project PERCEIVE, he works on the development of methods and tools to predict and simulate pigment colour changes in artworks. He has co-authored over 30 peer-reviewed publications on spectroscopy, colour ageing, and digital heritage science.

Topic: Colour change on works on paper and paintings

Content of the webinar

This episode is dedicated to two complementary computational approaches for studying the temporal evolution of Edvard Munch's *The Scream* (ca. 1910) and its changing appearance due to the effects of light, moisture, and material ageing. The first approach combines historical black and white photography with recent multispectral imaging to detect colour changes in the painting over time. By simulating the spectral response of the 1938 orthochromatic photograph from modern spectral data, and calibrating it with historic film sensitivity curves, we reveal significant lightness differences that point to fading of yellows and unexpected brightening of blues—phenomena that refine our understanding of the material ageing of the work. The second approach focuses on colour reconstruction using four historical colour photographs from 1971, 1989, 1993, and 2003. To address the challenges of film degradation, the method employs stable reference areas of the painting for advanced colour correction, enabling more faithful digital renderings of its appearance at several points in the 20th century. Together, these methods provide a pluralistic and data-driven framework for digitally reconstructing the past appearances of *The Scream*, demonstrating how integrating historical photographs with advanced spectral and computational imaging can open new perspectives for cultural heritage research.

[1.8 SimTex: Virtual 3D Restoration and Simulation of Fading in Fugitive Textiles](#)

Link <https://youtu.be/VYoJi-TioU4?si=cVBgv25nNmtXG-4U>

Date 15th October

Speakers & Abstract: Neil Saptarshi Sinha (Fraunhofer IGD), Irina Ciortan (NTNU)

Simulating the discolouration of cultural heritage garments provides valuable insights into their history and supports their preservation. For this purpose, digital methods provide innovative solutions

that can leverage the realism of aging processes without causing damage to the artifact. In this work, we propose a method to render colour changes in two fugitive textiles housed at the Victoria and Albert Museum. We use a combination of novel atlas-based material segmentation and colour restoration approaches to transfer appearance from textile mock-ups to the 3D models of the garments. The fading effects are induced with accelerated aging on mock-ups that are chemical proxies of the historic garments, with their aging monitored colourimetrically and spectrally, and their appearance measured with a total appearance capture device. Our proposed approach generates a colour-cue-based segmentation map over a 3D surface, followed by appearance transfer to segmented regions from mock-ups and fading simulations from spectral unmixing, along with appearance-aware restoration optimized using a reference image. By facilitating appearance-aware fading simulation in virtual 3D models in an interactive app, our approach supports a realistic visualization of colour change in the past and the future. We evaluate our method on two heritage garments - a 20th century kimono and a 19th century Victorian dress featuring different fabrics (silk and cotton) and dyed with natural and synthetic materials. In accordance with data collected through scientific analysis measurements, the proposed method effectively transfers a visual appearance that is both plausible and consistent with the data, providing both specialists and lay audiences with a range of fading simulations to support interpretation and restoration decisions.

Saptarshi Neil Sinha is a research associate at the Fraunhofer Institute for Computer Graphics Research, Darmstadt, Germany. He holds a master's degree in computer science (2016) from the University of Saarland, where he completed his thesis in the field of computer graphics in collaboration with DFKI (Saarland) and the Max Planck Institute for Computer Science. After that, he worked in the industry developing applications in the field of real-time rendering on the web. In the Visual Computing System Technologies department at Fraunhofer IGD, he contributed to 3D streaming and real-time web rendering for the Instant3DHub project, collaborating closely with the automotive industry. Since 2021, he has been part of the Virtual and Augmented Reality department at Fraunhofer IGD, focusing on projects related to the automotive industry, cultural heritage, and bioeconomy. His research interests include scene digitization, analysis, and editing utilizing learning-based approaches, synthetic data generation, and real-time rendering, leveraging spatial data structures for streaming large 3D models.

Irina-Mihaela Ciortan is a Postdoctoral Researcher at the Colourlab, NTNU, where she previously completed a PhD degree in Computer Science (2023), with a thesis entitled "Spectral and Multi-light Imaging for Cultural Heritage: Material Analysis and Appearance Reconstruction". Irina holds a joint MSc diploma in Spectral Science and Multimedia Technologies awarded by the 4-university Erasmus Mundus Consortium "Colour in Informatics and Media Technology" (2013) and a BSc in Computer Science issued by the Faculty of Cybernetics, Statistics and Informatics in Bucharest, Romania (2011). Currently, Irina works in the HORIZON EU project PERCEIVE (Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Coloured Collections through AI and Virtual Experiences), she is mainly capturing and analysing visual data towards designing computational methods for the digital simulation of colour changes in various artworks: paintings, textiles, historical photographs.

Lucia Burgio is Lead Conservation Scientist at the Victoria and Albert Museum, London, where she heads the Science Laboratory and directs the scientific analysis and research of the V&A collections. She has published extensively on her special interests, which include historical pigments and American and Asian lacquer. She is a Fellow of the Royal Society of Chemistry and is the UK representative to the EuChemS Working Party on Chemistry for Cultural Heritage. She chairs the Royal Society of Chemistry's Heritage Science Expert Working Group, using this position to promote

the role and importance of analytical science in the cultural heritage sector and disseminate heritage science to various audiences.

Topic: Colour change modelling in fugitive textiles

Content of the webinar

The eighth webinar, moderated by Lucia Burgio, Lead Scientist at the Victoria and Albert Museum, and chair of Scenario 3, was titled **SimTex: Virtual 3D Restoration and Simulation of Fading in Fugitive Textiles** and was presented by Saptarshi Neil Sinha and Irina-Mihaela Ciortan. They presented a digital method for simulating colour fading in two textile collection items from the Victoria and Albert Museum—a 20th-century kimono and a 19th-century Victorian dress. Accelerated aging was applied to chemically matched textile mock-ups, and their changes were monitored using spectral and colourimetric analysis. These fading effects were then transferred to 3D models through atlas-based segmentation and appearance-aware restoration. The approach enabled interactive visualisation of past and future colour changes, supporting interpretation and conservation. Evaluations showed that the method produced visually plausible and data-consistent simulations, offering valuable tools for both experts and the public. By allowing audiences to witness the garments' transformation over time, the research deepened public understanding and fostered a renewed sense of care and emotional connection to these fragile historical objects.

[1.9 An Integrated Approach to Reconstructing Ancient Polychromy on Marble Sculpture](#)

Link <https://youtu.be/VP7hkDFrf2g?si=txmEhscsQtA2BB6>

Date 18th November

Speakers & Abstract: Donata Magrini (CNR) Paolo Liverani (UNIFI)

The effort to recover the original appearance of ancient statuary is a profoundly complex and fascinating pursuit. It is a rigorous, interdisciplinary process. This work requires the integration of archaeology, heritage science, and historical research to ensure that any reconstruction is scientifically grounded in tangible evidence, thereby avoiding mere speculation. In this webinar the speakers will explore the methodologies that allow us to study and reconstruct the vibrant colors of antiquity.

Paolo Liverani studied Classics at the Sapienza University of Rome with a PhD in 1991 in Ancient Topography. His major research interests include ancient topography of Rome, Latium and Etruria; Roman state art; polychromy of ancient Roman sculpture; spolia; history of the archaeological collections and museums of Rome. From 1986 to 2005, he was Curator of Classical Antiquities at the Vatican Museum. Since November 2005 he is Professor for the Topography of Ancient Italy at the University of Florence. He is currently Chair of the Department of History, Archaeology, Geography, Fine and Performing Arts at the University of Florence. He is member of the Academia Europaea, and the Pontifical Roman Academy of Archaeology; corresponding member of the Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei, the Archaeological Institute of America, the German Archaeological Institute, the National Italian Institute of Etruscan Studies, and the Société National des Antiquaires de France; honorary fellow of the British School at Rome.

Donata Magrini is a researcher at the Italian National Research Council's Institute of Heritage Science (CNR-ISPC) in Florence. She holds an MSc in Heritage Science and a PhD in Chemical Sciences. Her research activity is characterized by a multi-disciplinary approach that spans various areas of Heritage Science. Her main research interests and expertise focus on applying non-invasive

and micro-invasive techniques to characterize polychrome artworks and study their conservation state. She has a specific research line dedicated to the archaeometry of original polychromy on classical statuary, using a combination of imaging techniques and portable non-destructive (ND) techniques. She is actively involved in national and international research programs and has coordinated national research projects related to the diagnostics and conservation of heritage materials.

Topic Reconstructing Ancient Polychromy on Marble Sculpture

Content of the webinar

The process of reconstructing lost polychromy on ancient statuary is a complex, interdisciplinary effort that combines archaeology with heritage science and historical research. This integrated approach ensures that reconstructions are not speculative but are scientifically grounded in tangible evidence. The first part of the webinar explores approaches and examples dealing with successful reconstruction based on the synergistic comparison of three key data sources: archaeometric data, historical sources, and iconographic parallels. The second contribution provides a comprehensive overview of how archaeometry is used to investigate and document the lost polychromy on ancient stone objects. The presentation will explore the non-invasive and micro-invasive analytical methods that allow for the identification of original pigment traces, providing crucial insights into ancient artistic practices and material technology

1.10 Introduction to the Colour Knowledge Repository

Link https://youtu.be/TSTF-WsXr18?si=Lif_3ACfCHpCHpt

Date 25th November

Speakers & Abstract: Sophia Sotiropoulou & Marius Pitikakis

The Colour Knowledge Repository, a key output of the PERCEIVE project, is a powerful data management system that collects, organises, and openly shares colour-related resources in cultural heritage artworks. As a collaborative research environment, the Repository brings together a diverse community of stakeholders, including colour experts, heritage and data scientists, museum curators, conservators, exhibition designers, and education and communication professionals, working across physical and digital cultural heritage domains. Initially designed to support the PERCEIVE working groups sharing data and resources for heritage objects ranging from ancient polychrome sculptures and delicate painted surfaces to dyed textiles and historical films, our goal is to expand this community. We warmly welcome all researchers and museum professionals interested in colour-related themes in heritage collections to join and contribute to dedicated thematic communities. Finally, this webinar provides a comprehensive introduction to the Repository's scope, structure, and content, detailing its technical architecture and infrastructure. We'll highlight key features, present practical use cases for various user profiles, and invite interested researchers and professionals to access and test the platform firsthand.

Sophia Sotiropoulou is Assistant Professor at the Hellenic Open University (HOU), School of Applied Arts and Sustainable Design and Research Associate at the Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser of the Foundation of Research and Technology – Hellas (IESL- FORTH). She is a physicist; post graduated in Physical methods in Archaeology and Museography and holds a PhD in colour data analysis of heritage objects. Devoted to heritage science, she conducts research and teaches the development of analytical strategies and methodologies for studying and monitoring a wide range of archaeological materials, artworks, heritage objects and structures. Her specialism is the

characterisation of the optical, chemical and visually perceptible properties of coloured and painted surfaces on heritage objects. She is also interested in communicating scientific data to a wider audience, exploring novel approaches, and promoting cross-disciplinary understanding and the co-creation of new cultural content. In PERCEIVE Project she is leading WP3 on Material modelling and Data management.

Marios Pitikakis is a Lecturer - Lab Teaching staff at the Computer Science Department, University of Crete (CSD-UoC), and a Research Associate at the Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser of the Foundation of Research and Technology Hellas (IESL-FORTH).

He received his Ph.D. from the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Thessaly, Greece and holds a B.Sc. in Mathematics and a B.Sc. in Computer Science from University of Crete, Greece. He has worked with several Research Institutes in Greece and Italy and has extensive research and development experience in EU and National funded projects. He has over 25 refereed publications in international journals, conferences and edited volumes. His research interests include Semantic Data Management, Knowledge Bases and Decision Support Systems, Data/Information Analysis, Medical Informatics with emphasis on Computer Aided Diagnosis/Detection, Medical image processing and 3D visualization, use of XR technologies in education. In PERCEIVE, he is responsible for the development of the Colour Knowledge Repository.

Topic Introduction to the CKR

Content of the webinar

In this webinar, we offered an introduction to the Colour Knowledge Repository (CKR) and its scope. The objective of the CKR is to create a data management environment that supports the entire data lifecycle from acquisition to processing and beyond. The technical architecture, the infrastructure and the content of the CKR were presented, and how it can support FAIR data and their reuse. Finally, a live demonstration was presented to familiarize attendees with the key features and functionalities of the Repository (searching, browsing & accessing datasets and their metadata, uploading new records & managing existing ones, communities & collaboration), discuss practical use cases for different user profiles, and invite interested researchers and professionals to access it.

[1.11 Prototyping Caring Hybrid experiences for Coloured Museum Collections](#)

Link: [Webinar Event](#) (YouTube link TBD)

Date 27th January 2026

Abstract. This webinar will be focused on the design of hybrid experiences for coloured museum collections, where theory, scientific research, and interaction design converge to rethink the role of the visitor in museums. It will take place on the 27th of January, split in two sections: Prototyping Caring Hybrid Experiences for Coloured Museum Collections

Speakers & Abstract: Bonifazi, Pescarin, Veggi (CNR ISPC), Olsson (MUNCH)

The concept of care in Cultural Heritage is evolving from a specialized professional duty into a shared practice of citizenship. Building on research from the PERCEIVE prototype framework, this session explores how hybrid design can foster a "sense of care" by connecting visitors emotionally and intellectually to the risks faced by coloured collections. Through the "**Echoes of Loss**" prototype, heritage is presented not as a static relic, but as a fragile and irreplaceable resource that requires

collective advocacy and engagement. The webinar demonstrates how making scientific processes visible and inviting visitors to "care" for lost polychromy can transform the museum visit.

Federica Bonifazi is a PhD student in Heritage Science at La Sapienza University of Rome, specializing in Digital Archaeology for scientific communication. As a Research Fellow at CNR-ISPC, she contributes to the EU project PERCEIVE, focusing on 3D digitalization, interface design for diagnostic tools (MuLaX Tool), and the design of interactive XR prototypes. She holds a BA in Cultural Heritage and a MA in Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge at the University of Bologna, where she graduated with a thesis on the virtual reconstruction of ancient polychromy.

Nynne Ryhl Olsson holds a Master's degree in Art History from the University of Copenhagen. She works in the field of art mediation at MUNCH as Concepts Developer Learning. In this role, Nynne collaborates with exhibitions and projects such as PERCEIVE, focusing on meaningful and engaging interactions with visual art by creating engaging experiences through narrative, text, space and program.

Sofia Pescarin is research director at CNR - ISPC in Florence, chairing the group within the Digital Heritage Innovation Lab. She received her PhD in "History and Computing" and a master in "Exhibition Design". She is also professor of Interaction Media Design at the University of Bologna. She authored and curated more than 150 scholarly publications and is Chief Editor of the Journal Elsevier "Digital Application in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage" (DAACH). She coordinated and worked in different projects, also at a European level, concerning virtual tools for cultural heritage. Currently she is the scientific coordinator of the EU project PERCEIVE.

Manuele Veggi is Doctoral Researcher at CNR – ISPC and PhD Student in Heritage Science (Sapienza University of Rome). His research lies at the intersection of interaction design, behavioural science and visitor studies and, in the framework of the PERCEIVE project, he contributed to the studies on the sense of care. He graduated with honours in digital heritage and multimedia at MA "Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge" at the University of Bologna, where he attended the honour school of the university specialising in digital art history. He is currently Visting PhD at the Laboratory for Experimental Museology at EPFL, Lausanne.

Topic: Caring prototype

Content of the webinar

The "Echoes of Loss" prototype translates the philosophical and psychological concept of care into a tangible museum experience, moving beyond the traditional view that conservation is solely the responsibility of experts.

The user journey is structured to move participants through three distinct phases: emotional connection, knowledge building, and active study. It begins with an evocative video narrative that contrasts the vibrant, reconstructed past of the Temple of Isis with the "sadness of loss" found in its current, colourless state.

This emotional foundation leads into the **Colour Lab**, where visitors interact with 3D-printed replicas and diagnostic tools, and are introduced to the complex world of diagnostics for the study and reconstruction of lost polychromy, particularly referring to the analyses conducted on the Venus Anadyomene. The underlying idea is to guide the visitor through a multi-stage journey into the intricate phases of scientific research, without which we would not have the opportunity to reconstruct the original colours of the sculptures.

In this case, three specific types of investigations have been offered to public: XRF, optical microscopy, and luminescence in the visible spectrum. These three techniques have been integrated

into a single prototype, allowing the visitor to engage through physical interaction in the complex realm of polychromy research, actively participating via a simulation created through the reconstruction of the technical instrumentation.

The experience ends with "**Echoes of Colours**," an interactive projection mapping where visitors must physically "lift" objects to reveal hypothetical reconstructions on a statue. The weight of these objects serves as a metaphor for the effort and responsibility intrinsic to the act of care.

[1.12 Prototyping Authentic Hybrid experiences for Coloured Museum Collections](#)

Link: [Webinar Event](#) (YouTube link TBD)

Speakers & Abstract: Città, Massidda, Pescarin (CNR ISPC)

This webinar examines the concept of authenticity in cultural heritage through the lens of "The Gifts of Isis," a prototype that translates theoretical frameworks into a practical museum application. The session explores how hybrid design can move beyond traditional conservation to create meaningful connections between visitors and archaeological collections. Focusing on "The Gifts of Isis", an interactive prototype based on the Temple of Isis in Pompeii we examine a design framework that activates authenticity across three distinct dimensions:

- Self: Personal resonance through role-playing and individual task.
- Others: Relation with other players fostered by the recreation of the collective ritual and shared decision-making.
- World: Environmental and historical embeddedness achieved through multisensory storytelling, 3d reconstructions and projections.

The session details the visitor's journey from "learning through doing" (reconstructing frescoes and architectural plans) to "embodying the past" (engaging in sensory rituals involving touch, scent, and sound).

Giuseppe Città holds a degree in Philosophy and History of Ideas (specializing in the linguistic-epistemological curriculum) and a PhD in Cognitive Sciences. His research focuses on the intersection of **Cognitive Sciences and serious games**. In particular, his interests center on the cognitive processes involved in learning/gaming phases and the cognitive aspects underlying the design of serious games.

Marcello Massidda is a Researcher at CNR-ISPC and a PhD student in Heritage Science at Sapienza University of Rome. His work focuses on the design and development of web-based 3D applications for cultural heritage, with particular attention to UI/UX design, hybrid experience design. His research bridges interaction design, digital prototyping, and immersive technologies applied to museum and exhibition contexts. He holds a BA in Industrial Design from the University of Florence, a MA with honours in Communication Design from ISIA Florence and he has worked as a professional designer and developer in the digital cultural heritage sector.

Sofia Pescarin is research director at CNR - ISPC in Florence, chairing the group within the Digital Heritage Innovation Lab. She received her PhD in "History and Computing" and a master in "Exhibition Design". She is also professor of Interaction Media Design at the University of Bologna. She authored and curated more than 150 scholarly publications and is Chief Editor of the Journal Elsevier "Digital Application in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage" (DAACH). She coordinated and

worked in different projects, also at a European level, concerning virtual tools for cultural heritage. Currently she is the scientific coordinator of the EU project PERCEIVE.

Topic: Authenticity prototype

Content of the webinar:

"The Gifts of Isis" translates the complex theoretical concept of authenticity into a practical, hybrid museum application. Authenticity is redefined here not as a fixed attribute of a historical object, but as a relational quality produced through the interaction between the visitor and the heritage. This framework is structured around three core dimensions: the Self, which focuses on personal resonance and emotional engagement; Others, which emphasizes social dialogue and collaborative meaning-making; and the World, which ensures historical coherence and a multisensory atmosphere.

The application consists of an interactive, multiplayer and multi-sensory experience designed for three participants at a time, revolving around life at the temple of Isis in Pompeii after the earthquake of 62 CE

The user journey begins with a narrator inviting the three participants to choose a symbolic gift, among Wisdom, Creativity and Patience, which assigns them a historical role, respectively Architect, Painter or Sculptor. This initial phase encourages learning through doing, as players engage in minigames on tablets according to their role (*Self*), such as reassembling the frescoes of the temple's porticus or identifying iconographic details. As the experience progresses, the players manage to reconstruct the temple and start immersing in its ritual life through wall projections, immersive storytelling and sensory, collaborative tasks (*World*). The characters evolve into ritual figures like the Priestess, Musician, or Devotee and are asked to work together to complete rituals using their senses. By incorporating tactile exploration of fabrics, the scent of sacred perfumes, and the sound of 3D-printed musical instruments, the prototype expands the sensory horizon beyond vision. Success in these tasks depends on shared negotiation and dialogue, fulfilling the *Others* dimension by transforming the museum visit into a communal act of discovery.

[1.13 Tools and Services for the Design of Digital Heritage Experiences. The PERCEIVE Design ToolBox](#)

Link: [Webinar Event](#) (YouTube link TBD)

Date: 28 January

Speakers & Abstract Massidda, Pescarin, Veggi (CNR ISPC), Zapf (Fraunhofer IGD)

This webinar presents PERCEIVE Design ToolBox an integrated suite of tools for digital heritage experiences. The three collaborative tools, the CoDesign Tool, the Prototyper and the Cultural Heritage Experiments Configuration Kit (checkK), support curators, heritage practitioners and creative industries in designing, prototyping and assessing hybrid and immersive heritage applications.

The CoDesign Tool facilitates early-stage ideation through a card-based methodology that structures collaborative workshops around key experiential values. The Prototyper, a web-based 3D authoring platform, enables non-programmers to configure and simulate spatial layouts, interaction flows, and multimedia content in virtual exhibition environments. checkK wraps these 3D environments with experimental control capabilities, allowing researchers to conduct rigorous empirical studies on visitor behavior without coding expertise.

Together, these tools establish a continuum from conceptualization through prototyping to empirical evaluation. The webinar will demonstrate practical workflows across the toolbox, discuss findings

from classroom testing and real-world deployments, and present opportunities for adoption within cultural institutions and research contexts.

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Sofia Pescarin is research director at CNR - ISPC in Florence, chairing the group within the Digital Heritage Innovation Lab. She received her PhD in “History and Computing” and a master in “Exhibition Design”. She is also professor of Interaction Media Design at the University of Bologna. She authored and curated more than 150 scholarly publications and is Chief Editor of the Journal Elsevier “Digital Application in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage” (DAACH). She coordinated and worked in different projects, also at a European level, concerning virtual tools for cultural heritage. Currently she is the scientific coordinator of the EU project PERCEIVE.

Manuele Veggi is Doctoral Researcher at CNR – ISPC and PhD Student in Heritage Science (Sapienza University of Rome). His research lies at the intersection of interaction design, behavioural science and visitor studies and, in the framework of the PERCEIVE project, he contributed to the studies on the sense of care. He graduated with honours in digital heritage and multimedia at MA “Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge” at the University of Bologna, where he attended the honour school of the university specialising in digital art history. He is currently Visting PhD at the Laboratory for Experimental Museology at EPFL, Lausanne.

Andreas Zapf is an Interaction Designer and researcher at the Fraunhofer Institute for Computer Graphics Research IGD in Darmstadt. He is enthusiastic about intuitive design with a focus on usability, user experience and human interaction as well as creating well-designed user interfaces. He has a B.A. in Media Design (Hof University) and gained his first experience as a research assistant during this period. Since then, he has worked in the field of research particularly in the area of cultural heritage and for industrial partners.

Topic: PERCEIVE Design Toolbox

Content of the webinar

The webinar opened with a brief overview of the PERCEIVE Design Toolbox, situating the three tools within the broader context of hybrid exhibition design challenges. The introduction outlined common barriers faced by cultural institutions—coordinating interdisciplinary teams, translating conceptual ideas into tangible prototypes, and conducting empirical evaluation without programming skills—and presented the integrated workflow as a continuum from ideation through spatial prototyping to rigorous assessment.

The first segment introduced the physical CoDesign Tool, demonstrating its card-and-board system for structuring collaborative ideation sessions. The presentation walked through the two main phases: building the Design Brief and Ideation/Storyboarding, with particular attention to the Audience Goals stage featuring dedicated card decks focused on Authenticity and Sense of Care. The demonstration illustrated how the game-like format makes design processes accessible regardless of prior expertise, encouraging inclusive collaboration among curators, designers, educators, and technologists.

Findings from evaluation workshops highlighted improved clarity, reduced cognitive load, and more balanced team participation compared to the tool's predecessor.

The second segment presented the web-based version of the CoDesign Tool, showcasing how the digital platform extends accessibility to hybrid and remote collaboration contexts. Key features were demonstrated: remote collaboration from any device, integrated moderator roles, live progress tracking, expanded card interactions with voting mechanisms, and seamless integration with other PERCEIVE tools. The presentation emphasized how the digital version maintains the collaborative dynamics of the physical format while addressing logistical challenges of distributed teams and session documentation.

The final segment presented the Prototyper and checkK as complementary tools completing the design-to-evaluation workflow. The Prototyper demonstration showcased its widget-based architecture, illustrating how users can configure 3D exhibition spaces through drag-and-drop asset placement, viewpoint definition, and VR preview modes without coding. Real-world application examples from PERCEIVE's Final Exhibition prototypes demonstrated iterative configuration of spatial layouts and multimedia content. The checkK demonstration focused on transforming ATON-based environments into controlled experimental settings, walking through the workflow from protocol configuration through experiment execution to data export. Findings from the pilot study using the Aldrovandi exhibition digital twin demonstrated both feasibility and identified areas for ongoing refinement.

2. Analytics

2.1 Social Media: Strategy, Activities and Results

Ivana Cerato, CNR-ISPC Federica Bonifazi CNR-ISPC

The social media campaign supporting the PERCEIVE webinar series was designed with multiple objectives: to maximise participation in live events, ensure the dissemination of training content to diverse target groups, build and consolidate a professional community interested in colour in cultural heritage, and foster networking among institutions, researchers, and professionals in the field.

- The strategy adopted a differentiated multi -platform approach, leveraging the specific characteristics of each social channel:
- Facebook – used for broad dissemination to both general and professional audiences, focusing on visually engaging and easily shareable content.
- LinkedIn - the primary channel for professional and academic communication, highlighting technical and scientific topics, digital tools, and research outcomes.
- Instagram – aimed at a younger audience, with an emphasis on visual and creative aspects of cultural heritage through coordinated and aesthetically curated posts.
- YouTube – serving as a repository for asynchronous learning and permanent access to training content.

Monthly Newsletter - as a complementary, direct communication instrument to maintain continuity between webinars and ensure targeted outreach to the project's professional network. The newsletter provided a curated space for announcements, summaries, and access to training resources, reinforcing the visibility of each webinar and sustaining engagement over time. It acted as both an entry point (pre-event registration and awareness) and a follow-up channel (sharing recordings and materials), integrating seamlessly with the social media timeline.

Each webinar was supported by a three-phase communication cycle:

- Pre-announcement (7–10 days before): launch post including programme, speakers, and themes.
- Reminder (1–3 days before): follow-up post with registration link and countdown.
- Post-event follow-up (within 48 hours): publication of the full video on YouTube and cross-sharing across social media for on-demand viewing.

Parallel to this, the newsletter followed a complementary editorial rhythm: early issues (March) introduced the training series and invited registration, while subsequent editions (May–June–September) disseminated video recordings and maintained the link with subscribers even during non-active months. This ensured a stable flow of information, high open rates, and a consistent sense of continuity across the project’s communication ecosystem.

2.1.2. Activities Implemented

Between April and October 2025, corresponding to the first eight webinars in the series, the following activities were carried out:

Content Production

- 14 original posts distributed across Facebook, Instagram, and LinkedIn.
- Dedicated graphics created for each webinar, ensuring visual consistency.
- Editing and publication of 6 full-length webinar videos on YouTube, up to date, whereas the remaining webinars will be progressively published before the end of the project.
- Extraction of image and content highlights for teaser or reminder posts.
- Six newsletters produced between March and September 2025, combining event promotion, video dissemination, and community updates.

Publishing and Distribution

- Coordinated posting across three main platforms (four including YouTube).
- Adaptation of tone and format according to platform conventions.
- Strategic scheduling of announcements, reminders, and follow-ups.
- Cross-posting with interlinked content to guide audiences between platforms.

Community Management

- Daily monitoring of comments and private messages.
- Prompt responses to technical and logistical questions (access, schedule, materials).
- Moderation of discussions and re-sharing of related content between webinars.

The content covered topics such as PERCEIVE theory and data acquisition for colour change simulation (webinars 1 and 5), game-based learning experiences for conservation awareness (webinar 2), innovative diagnostic techniques such as MULAX and non-invasive textile analysis (webinars 3, 6, and 8), the documentation and virtual restoration of Autochromes (webinar 4), and computational colour reconstruction from historical photographic archives (webinar 7).

2.1.3 Quantitative Results and Engagement

Facebook demonstrated the greatest organic dissemination potential, with peak reach exceeding 4,000 users for the most viral posts (webinar 1: 4,304; webinar 2: 3,766) and an overall average of 1,037 views per post. The average interaction rate was 4 reactions and 6 shares per post, indicating strong audience engagement and spontaneous content diffusion.

On **LinkedIn**, posts achieved an average of 397 impressions and 33 interactions per post, with notable peaks for webinar 1 (Theory and Data Acquisition, 909 impressions, 100 engagements), webinar 3 (MULAX, 721 impressions, 50 engagements), and webinar 6 (Photofading Dyes, 394 impressions, 36 engagements). These results highlight sustained interest in scientific and technology-oriented content.

Instagram contributed to audience diversification, averaging 81 post views and 127 likes per publication. The highest engagement was recorded for webinar 7 (The Scream), demonstrating that visually compelling and iconic artworks generate stronger performance on this aesthetic-driven platform.

YouTube played a complementary and essential role as a permanent training archive, enabling on-demand access to the webinars. The first six videos published (April–September 2025) accumulated over 290 total views, averaging 55 minutes per video, with peaks for webinars 1 and 2. This ensured international reach, especially among users in different time zones and professionals unable to attend live sessions.

The **newsletter** consistently achieved open rates between 50% and 60%, above the average for institutional mailing lists, with moderate but steady click-throughs (1–5 per issue) strictly related to links referring to webinars. The subscriber base grew by 27% over six months (from 83 recipients in March to 106 in September), confirming continuous community expansion and effective integration with social media outreach.

2.1.4 Qualitative Analysis: Comments and Feedback

Qualitative analysis shows that engagement focused mainly on likes and shares, rather than extended comments. Users primarily used social media to:

- Express interest and appreciation.
- Share information with professional networks.
- Save posts as reminders for later participation or viewing.

The most engaging topics were:

- Iconic case studies (The Scream).
- Innovative digital tools (MULAX, non-invasive techniques).
- Interdisciplinary content combining conservation, technology, and communication.

The interactions indicate three main audience segments: museum professionals, researchers and academics in heritage science, and digital specialists in cultural heritage.

The high number of shares on Facebook and impressions on LinkedIn suggest that the content was perceived as professionally valuable and worth sharing within expert networks.

2.1.5 Summary and Conclusions

The social media campaign supporting the PERCEIVE Training Programme effectively achieved its objectives of dissemination, engagement, and community building.

Data confirm a significant overall reach (over 13,000 cumulative views on Facebook) and a steady interaction rate, demonstrating genuine interest in the project's themes.

Strengths identified

- Multi-platform approach reaching diversified targets.

- High-quality scientific content generating professional interest.
- Structured temporal strategy (announcement–reminder–follow-up).
- YouTube integration ensuring permanent access to training materials.

Areas for improvement

- Increase the production of short-form videos (30–90s) for social media.
- Encourage more discussion through clearer calls-to-action and interactive posts.
- Maintain consistent communication between webinars.
- Standardise the use of project hashtags and explore external collaborations.

The experience gained through the first eight webinars provides solid operational and methodological foundations to further optimise future communication activities, confirming the effectiveness of the integrated social media + YouTube approach as a tool for scientific dissemination and professional training in the cultural heritage sector.

2.2 Cross-Platform Comparative Analysis and Strategic Recommendations

KPI Summary Table

Platform	Posts / Videos analysed	Average Reach	Average Engagement	Key Notes
Facebook	14 posts	1,037	6 shares / 4 likes	High variability, effective reminder strategy
LinkedIn	13 posts	397	33 interactions	Qualified engagement, professional audience
Instagram	14 posts	81	127 likes	Strong visual impact on iconic artworks
YouTube	6 videos	49 views/video	–	Permanent training archive, asynchronous access
Newsletter	6 issues	50-60% open rate	1-5 link clicks/issue	Stable readership, expanding mailing list

2.2.1 Comparative Analysis and Insights

The comparative analysis highlights the distinct strategic role of each platform:

- Facebook – broad dissemination and viral reach.
- LinkedIn – professional and academic communication hub.
- Instagram – project visual identity and outreach to younger audiences.
- YouTube – long-term educational repository.
- Newsletter – continuity and direct engagement with the project community.

Key Observations:

- Posts featuring iconic artworks and vivid graphics achieved the highest performance.
- The announcement + reminder combination increased engagement by 30–40%.
- Interdisciplinary topics combining art, science, and technology attracted the most attention.

- The limited number of comments reflects silent professional engagement, typical of LinkedIn usage.
- Email communication reinforced audience loyalty and sustained attention during periods of lower social media activity.

Operational Recommendations:

- Publish intermediate content between webinars to sustain engagement.
- Strengthen Instagram-specific strategies (Stories, Reels, carousels).
- Extract short clips from webinars as teaser videos.
- Standardise hashtags (#PERCEIVEproject, #ColourHeritage, #MuseumTech).
- Include clear CTAs (“Register”, “Watch the replay”, “Share with a colleague”).
- Promote user-generated content and interactive polls to foster participation.

Continue integrating newsletter and social channels to ensure continuity and cross-platform conversion.

2.2.2 Overall Impact and Future Perspectives

The social media strategy has acted as a key impact multiplier for the PERCEIVE Training Programme, transforming a series of specialist webinars into a broad, long-lasting dissemination initiative.

Main Results

- Establishment of an active professional community.
- Organic reach amplified up to tenfold beyond direct participants.
- Creation of a permanent educational archive on YouTube.
- Positioning of PERCEIVE as a reference project in the colour heritage field.

Future Outlook

- Consolidate the growing follower base and active community.
- Integrate evergreen content marketing and dedicated newsletters.
- Develop a structured online community (e.g., LinkedIn group).
- Implement advanced analytics tools to track user journeys.

In a context of fragmented attention and declining organic reach, the results achieved by PERCEIVE stand out for their quality, strategic coherence, and educational impact. The upcoming challenge will be to maintain and expand this communication momentum, capitalising on the best practices identified and strengthening the vibrant community that has grown around the project.